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State Estimation of Lithium-Ion-Batteries using Strain Gages

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During lithiation and delithiation of a lithium-ion battery (LIB), the anode can undergo a volume change of approximately 10%. This effect can be measured with strain gages. In this work, multiple cylindrical cell types have been equipped with strain gages. The strain of cylindrical cells, measured during charging and discharging cycles, exhibits a strong correlation with the lithiation state, indicated by a coefficient of 0.97. This information can be further utilized for State of Charge (SOC) estimation.

Introduction

As electric vehicles play a significant role in the climate crisis, battery technologies undergo a rapid development. For a reliable and safe application of LIBs, a precise state estimation is necessary. Currently, the State of X (SOX) of LIBs are determined based on voltage, current and temperature. The application of multiple sensor types enables more precise estimations, for not only first-life applications but also second-life integration of LIBs. In this study, strain gages have been applied to cylindrical cells to disclose the correlation between strain and SOC.

Experimental Setup

In this study, linear strain gages from Hottinger Brüel & Kjaer GmbH (HBM) have been selected to measure the strain on cylindrical cells. The strain gages have a measuring grid of 6 mm x 2.7 mm with a resistance of 120 Ohm. To achieve reproducible results, a contraption has been designed, as shown in Figure 1, that ensures consistent application of the strain gages in terms of location, orientation, and application force. Prior to the application of the strain gages, the cylindrical cells were discharged to 0% SOC and rested for 12 hours. The strain measurements were conducted with the cells standing freely and vertically. This ensures a free expansion in all directions. To supply and measure the strain gage signal, an amplifier from HBM was used. The strain gage was connected in a quarter-bridge configuration with a supply voltage of 2.5 mV.

Figure 1. Experimental Setup

Measurements and results

The first measurements were done with Samsung INR18650 29E cylindrical cells. The cells, based on lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxides (NMC), have a nominal capacity of 2.85 Ah. For the measurements, the strain gage was applied with the previously described contraction on the center of the cell. Measurements on this cell type revealed an inverse strain behavior in the majority of the measurements, as shown in Figure 2(a). During charging, the strain decreased, and during discharging, the strain increased, which is contrary to what is reported in the literature^{1,2}. This behavior was observed at three different positions along the axis and circumference of the cell. Only when the strain gage covered the anode tab did the strain increase during charging and vice versa during discharging, as shown in Figure 2(b).

Figure 2. Strain Measurement Samsung 29E. (a) Inverse Strain and (b) Position on Anode Tab

The same procedure was repeated with Samsung INR18650 35E NMC cells, which have a nominal capacity of 3.5 Ah. This cell displayed the behavior observed in other studies. The results are shown in Figure 3. For this cell model, multiple positions were examined, all exhibiting similar characteristics. This indicates that the strain measurement of Samsung 35E cells is independent of the strain gage position. To avoid edge effects, strain gages for further measurements were applied at the middle position.

Figure 3. Strain Measurement Samsung 35E

To determine the cause of the difference between the cells, a post-mortem analysis was conducted. Both cells shared an identical design, with a positive tab along the entire length and a negative tab covering only the bottom half. As the cell designs were identical, they would not offer an explanation for the different strain curves. Therefore, the anode materials were investigated further. In fact, the Samsung 35E cell had an anode containing silicon, which explains the higher amplitudes and homogeneous strain throughout the cell. In contrast, no silicon was detected in the anode of the Samsung 29E cell, explaining its inhomogeneous behavior. This is due to silicon's much higher expansion rate, up to 300%, compared to graphite's expansion rate of up to 10%.

Conclusions and Outlook

This study has successfully proven, that strain values measured during charge and discharge on a cylindrical cell are closely linked to the SOC. Reproducible results were achieved only with anodes containing silicon. Cells with silicon displayed much higher amplitudes and a more homogeneous strain along the entire cell. In contrast, cells without silicon showed inhomogeneous and non-reproducible expansion. Additionally, strain values can be used to determine the state of health of a cell. It is also expected that strain values can identify safety-critical conditions, such as overcharging and overheating.

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References

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